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Abstract

Present paper is based on a qualitative study conducted to understand the construction and reconstruction of aspirations of Muslim adolescent girls, who are at the verge of completing their school education. This paper explores the transitional phase from school to life after school for 12 Muslim girls living in a Muslim dominated habitation of North East Delhi. The capital city, with three central universities and one state university, offers high aspirations to enter into college life but the spatial trajectories originating from segregated neighbourhood offers no “college-going culture” in the community for these girls. The paper is based on in-depth interviews with these 12 Muslim girls who completed their schooling from two neighbouring government-funded schools, one government school (all girls) and one government aided co-educational school. The unstructured interviews were carried out by keeping the interaction around the change or no change in their aspirations related to education and work, after finishing school education and what is their future course of actions. The girls’ responses reflect at girls’ gendered struggle within the family and neighbourhood to reconstruct their aspirations in confirmation with familial ethos of preserving social prestige in the community. The study observed that class followed by gender as two most influential factors affecting girls’ aspirations and the decisions made for the girls. It is because the contestations over exercising “choice” remain a class as well as gendered struggle within household and neighbourhood spaces for Muslim girls in the study. The paper also reflects on the larger discussion on the spatial and socio-economic factors contributing to the poor representation of Muslim girls in higher education. It is further followed by discussion on the contemporary state’s thrust on offering vocational courses to “empower” Muslim women, whose families have already been engaged in small-scale skilled businesses for ages. This idea further encourages the poor community members, and so Muslim girls to opt for learning some skill rather than going for higher education. The study finds reproduction of class and gender for these Muslim

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girls when it comes to adhering to the state's projected idea of empowerment. The entry into a university, especially for a regular graduate programme, remained an elusive goal for most of the girls interviewed. The paper thus finally concludes by stating that university still remains an exclusionary space for many girls belonging to the largest religious minority in terms of access to higher education.

Key Words: Muslim girls, Higher Education, Class, Gender, Aspirations, Choice, School

Context

The poor educational status of Indian Muslim women has been highlighted in many reports and studies from Towards Equality Report (1974-75) to Sachar Committee report (2005-06). It led the Indian government to take special and immediate measures to improve the community's socio-economic and educational status in the country through special initiatives under the 15-point programme (GoI, 2007). The main aim of the programme has been to ensure that the benefits of various schemes reach the disadvantaged minority community. The increase in Muslim girls' enrolment in school education has been the filter down impact of Right to Education (GoI, 2010) followed by scholarships offered under this 15-point programme beyond elementary education till the completion of school education. But in higher education, Muslim girls' enrolment shows drastic decline, showing a sudden break from Muslim girl students' aspirations to enter into college for higher education.

In an urban setting of Delhi, where physical and social spaces are expected to offer amalgamation of social groups, also carry structural boundaries formed broadly on class basis and specifically on caste and religion (here with special connotation to Hindu-Muslim). Some of the gated enclaves for Muslims in Delhi as quoted in Jameel (2017) work confirm to structural spatial segregation for Muslims in Delhi. Shahbadpur is one such Muslim dominated habitation, inhabited by more than 70 per cent Muslims¹ and mainly by working class residents.

Focusing on the Muslim adolescent girls living in this urban pocket, this paper tries to understand how aspirations related to higher education and work are constructed and reconstructed during the transition from school to life after school. Since, the transition from childhood to adolescence involved lived experiences of daily life that shape individual's understanding about the social world, higher secondary level schooling is one such crucial stage to understand how Muslim girls view their education and what are their aspirations related to education and career.

Researched Issue

The paper focuses on senior secondary girl students' aspirations related to higher education and work. It is important to understand the role of school as a state institution, especially to improve the educational status of Muslim girls in the light of recommendations made by Sachar Committee Report. In the process of studying how school is influencing girls' aspirations to enter higher education and work in their life after school, this paper is based on in-depth informal interactions with girls and their mothers. One of the expected aims of a state-run school is to offer physical and social space to prepare girls for higher education. Similarly, the role of family is expected to help in defining and realising the girls' aspirations related to education and employment. It was interesting to look at how the community's cultural dynamics get infused and sometimes conflict with the working-class concern of educating their children. The paper also reflects on the larger discussion on the spatial and socio-economic factors contributing to the poor representation of Muslim girls in higher education. This paper shows how these macro factors and micro level nuances at school and home are intertwined giving little or no space to contest or bargain to enter into the university space. It is further followed by discussion on the contemporary state's thrust on offering vocational courses to 'empower' Muslim women, whose families have already been engaged in small-scale skilled businesses for ages.

Researched landscape

Seelampur in North East Delhi is one of the civic-neglected and one of the spatial segregated sites (Jamil, 2011; 2017) that shelters a larger chunk of Delhi Muslim population, i.e., approximately 30 per cent. Interestingly, even within North East Delhi, one could observe differential access of civic infrastructure to habitation like the Hindu dominated posh area-Yamuna Vihar and the surrounding densely populated Muslim dominated habitation Shahbadpur. According to one of the community respondents, greater proportion of the original residents (mostly Muslims) were rehabilitated at the times of emergency in 1970s from walled city in Old Delhi, and rest around 30 per cent constituted the Muslim migrants from neighbouring state, Uttar Pradesh, the State that shares Delhi Eastern border (Baseline survey GOI, 2008; Jamil, 2011).

For the study, a government senior secondary school and a government aided school in a Muslim dominated habitation, Shahbadpur2, were undertaken. One school was a government girls' school, (GGS), an Urdu medium school with 98 per cent Muslim students where students largely belong to families with poor3 economic status. The other school was a government-aided school (GAS) which was co-educational with 100 per cent Muslim students, largely

belonging to families with relatively better⁴ economic status. At secondary level, GGS offers subject streams like Science, Commerce, Arts, and Vocational Stream while GAS offers Commerce and Art streams only.

Methodology

The data used for this paper is based on participant observations and informal interaction with the senior secondary girl students of government school and government aided school in schools as well as in the Muslim dominated habitation. These two schools—a government school and government-aided school, were claimed to be “good schools” as they both ensure “discipline” and “good results”—reported by the community members in the habitation. The girl respondents were grade XII students from two sections (Arts Stream and Vocational Stream- Beauty Culture and Health) in GGS and one Art section and Commerce section from GAS. Unstructured interviews were carried out with 12 girls by keeping the interaction around the change or no change in their aspirations related to education and work, after finishing school education and what is their future course of actions. Thematic and narrative analysis of the in-depth interviews was done to study the influence of school and family on the girls’ aspiration.

Girls in School

This section is based on participant observations and informal interactions reflecting on school and classroom practices, teachers’ opinions and expectations followed by girl aspirations. Government school had organised a career counselling programme for senior secondary girls and discussed the process of applying for higher education. The discussion centred around the process of seeking admission in college and professional education. The playground was mainly filled with Art and Vocational stream girls constituting eight sections out of total 12 sections of grade XII. The programme was largely lecture-based and the queries were posed mainly by Science and Commerce stream girl students. The Arts and Vocational Stream girls’ presence in big numbers did not translate into their voices in terms of their unresolved queries. Except for a few girls from Arts stream, no other girl from the two streams asked any question from the resource person. Three girls from Arts stream who asked questions had doubts about knowledge – how to seek admission in DIET (District Institute of Education and Training), college for regular graduation and ITI (Industrial Training Institute). In both the sections, It was observed that girl monitors of the two sections (Arts and Vocational) in government school wanted to opt for Science or Commerce at secondary level but higher cost involved (coaching/tuition) made them change their choice and so they chose Arts or Vocational Stream. The stream allocation (not selection) process at secondary level thus carries hierarchical

stratification on the basis of the cost involved which is followed by higher employment prospects. There is another filtering mechanism under which students, with scores less than 60 per cent (weak students) at secondary level, were allocated vocational stream. In this manner, girl students were being oriented to restructure their aspirations as per the conditions.

Shortage of teachers (English, Geography, and Math at higher secondary level) in the government school raised the anxiety level among girl students. Adding to those the Principal's instructions on preparing a list of weak students⁵ for board exams had further raised concerns over continuing their education in future. School teachers, under the guidance of the Principal, were used to identify ways to achieve 100 per cent passing results in board exams. This was the common aspect which the aided school was also aiming at. The government-aided school had no Science stream section but in commerce stream, there were only five girl students enrolled. In the period of three months of study in schools, no career counselling session, formal or informal, was organised in the aided school.

Apart from the above-mentioned aspects of schooling at senior secondary school, it was observed that school, in order to provide a safe and secured environment, had adopted strategies to keep girl students under discipline. Teachers' comments on discouraging big girls (secondary to higher secondary level) to play or roam in the playground in government school and constant gaze of CCTVs in the corridors of government aided school, had strengthened the gendered mobility for the girl students in both the schools.

Teachers' expectations were examined on the basis of teachers' responses on the girls' probability of continuing education, to which teachers had varied responses though all centred around the marks girl students will score in board examination, followed by parents' permission to continue education. Teachers were aware about parents' socio-economic and educational status and so at times also had influence on the level of expectations they had about girls' probability to continue education. On the question of parents attending PTM (Parent Teacher Meeting), one of the teachers replied, as in her own words, "*Are koi nahi aata madam, abhi bolen ki fellowship ka cheque milna hai to agle din pahunch jaayenge*" (Madam, nobody comes, and if we ask them to collect the fellowship cheque, they will come the very next day.) Another teacher respondent, who was the class teacher of the Vocational stream section, showed her concern by referring to the poor economic status of the parents, so the girls, if they learn the skill properly, can use it to earn and supplement in family income. Research observed that teachers' concern for the 'weak' students (especially in the English subject) during many instances of conversation projected weak expectations—like not believing in girls' ability to pass board exams.

On school/teacher-parent relationship, the class teacher of Vocational stream expressed more worries about girls passing in English. Her expression was – “*Are mein to chahti hoon ki ye sari ladkiyan pass ho jayen*” (I just want all girls to pass the board examination).

Interestingly, the teachers’ assumption or future expectation, on girls’ future steps after moving out from school was college or some vocational course, this contradicted with the researcher’s interaction with the girls. Researcher’s interaction with the girls revealed that in a class of 57, 43 (during classroom discussion) were not sure about whether they would be going for higher education. The uncertainty among girls also indicates lack of guidance over the possible future prospects after leaving school. The government aided school didn’t organise any counselling session to orient girls for life after school. Absence of any guidance regarding the career in school, and the poor educational status of the parents further offered no help; rather, subdued the aspirations of girl students.

Thus, school culture unable to build trust and confidence among girls to firmly decide on whether they would be able to go for higher education or not, especially in government school as in aided school, students with better educational and economic status of parents, responded more firmly on the question of getting enrolled in higher education and working towards their professional goal. Subsequent section is based on the second part of the field study conducted in the habitation.

Girl Students at Home

The life after school for the girl students was marked by the fact that they were missing their school in the habitation where college-going culture⁶ was hardly visible. During home visits, middle class parents’ anxieties of seeking admission in university was not found at all; instead, the few girls who wanted to pursue higher education were trying to convince their parents for the same. It was observed that the socially-attached meaning of being *dasvi aur barwin paas* (Xth and XII passed) for the parents is important and adequate for future marriage prospects in the community. This expectation corresponds with schools’ focus on passing the board examinations. At home, girls were not only adjusting with the new routine but there were few girls who were also exploring the possibilities of pursuing their aspirations.

It was the time when grade XII examination results were released, girls were very curious to know about their school classmates’ examination results. This offered them a good reason to visit their friends, one of the girl respondents accompanied me to another girls’ house, where she had asked her three other classmates to meet. The talk was centred around who passed. The girls, who scored good marks, showed more interest in sharing their marks and its

importance in gaining entry into a university. The next point of discussion among girls was about who all are going to the weekly market (Thursday market). The conversation continued for around 30-40 minutes, but there was no mention of enrolling for higher education or going to college by any girl. During an informal interaction, I asked them in the group about if they would like to continue further education. To this, however, they responded with a “yes” though one also added some conditions originating from their family/household expectations. No girl in the group expressed keenness about going to college.

In GGS, girls’ fathers were reluctant to let girls continue education in regular college, one of the girls shared she wants to earn pocket money by giving tuitions to children. Another girl respondent from the same school shared that she would apply in Jamia Millia Islamia (another central university) but via distance mode, as commuting every day to university would be difficult. Her elder sister had just completed her Master’s from the same university and was soon getting married. Among the six girls interviewed from the all girls’ government school, only two had taken admission in the undergraduate programme via distance mode, while the rest four had discontinued their education. Absence of girls’ college in the close vicinity of the habitation was cited by one mother as one of the reasons for not letting their daughters continue their education. The two co-educational colleges under the University of Delhi are located within four kilometres, while another all-girls’ college under the University of Delhi was located beyond six kilometres. The working-class parents living inside the habitation expressed reluctance in spending money and also sending their daughters to far off places for higher education.

One longitudinal study conducted in Karnataka on 36 adolescent girls observed that poverty and socioeconomic realities at the household level strongly affect conformity with discriminatory gender practices such as restricting girls’ mobility (Ramanaik et.al. 2018). The value placed on education differs with girls belonging to different socio-economic backgrounds like in this study, GGS girl respondents’ parents expressed more reluctance in letting their daughters continue education after finishing school in relation to girl respondents belonging to GAS.

Resisting for or Reconstructing Aspirations

The girls, when in school, expressed their desire to pursue further education, as they shared their fascinations about “going to college” during informal interactions in schools. Many were influenced by the popular imagination of a relatively restriction-free life of college. GGS girls, irrespective of the stream (Arts and Vocational), in total there were eight girls (9%) out of 86, who were

sure of continuing their education, while the rest were uncertain and wished their parents supported them in pursuing their aspirations to study further. In Vocational stream 19 girl students present expressed their desire to continue education or at least become economically independent by taking up the job of beautician.

In GAS, the girls from Arts stream shared similar status on seeking their parents' approval on letting them continue their education but with relative a greater number of girls (19%) was sure of continuing their education though all through distance mode. Whereas, in the Commerce section, barring one girl, the rest four clearly stated their aspiration of getting admission in a good college. Thus, on the issue of difference in aspirations, there was no difference in having aspirations to do well in future in both the schools and even within the streams. The difference was in the certainty of achieving them. Better economic status, accompanied with educational status of GAS girls, did help in raising the possibilities for them to pursue their career aspirations.

Another interesting observation was related to GGS girls' poor orientation about the future possibilities in education and career, as there were three girls who shared that they would like to become doctors one day. It reflected the lack of constructive interaction between teacher and student to orient girls about the stream and future scope under different streams at secondary level. Teaching profession was the most sought-after profession by many girls in both the school and also parents who supported girls for continuing education wanted them to become a teacher.

During home visits, the girls' interviews shared their aspirations to be self-reliant through education and work but the financial crisis is cited as the major reason of disapproval to continue education by parents. But there were some girls who showed ignorance or willingness to adjust themselves in the comfort zone of family and the community around. Out of the 12 girls interviewed, three (two from GGS and one from GAS) who managed to apply for the undergraduate programme via distance mode also stressed on their righteousness, keeping good conduct by not hiding anything from their parents, and following cultural norms in the neighbourhood and with relatives. All this according to them will make them "*sharif ladki*" (good girl), as according to them becoming a "*sharif ladki*" facilitates in making their voices heard within the family. The process is then followed by negotiations to pursue further education. The study showed that by following cultural norms of maintaining *purda* within the habitation, these girls in a way were maintaining the demographic religious identity (Desai and Gheda, 2014) which they don't mind giving up when they move in areas beyond their habitation. This shows how physical spaces carry social meaning that is within the community and outside the habitation for the girls. These girls

neither like to disrespect their community nor feel the need to comply with everything written in “*Hadees*”, rather want their own space to exercise their agency of being an integral human being.

In this way, home plays in consonance with school or vice versa in cultivating the gendered values by monitoring and moulding girl students’ aspirations as desired by the community’s need. Confirming to Shaban’s study (2016), this study conformed to the patriarchal attitudes of the family members that compel girls to restructure or be ignorant to their educational, personal and overall development. Some of the girls interviewed had brothers who withdrew from education after completing secondary education and had started working to supplement the household income. Thus, poor educational as well as economic status of parents and other household members had therefore made the overall household environment unfavourable of continuing daughters’ education. But even within this limiting environment, there were some girl students who were trying to redefine the socio-cultural restrictions by bargaining with the family members, like Amira, Tuba, and Amyra. Apart from that, there were cases like Najima, Nahid, Anam, and Iram, who had full support from their mothers to move forward with their aspirations; however, the case of Nahid and Najima differed due to their compelling family economic crisis that pushed them to enter the job market. Here, the girls were not relying on the skill they learned in their school, that is of beauty culture, rather girls from the vocational stream, were looking for either doing computer courses, or if done, then applying for a job like a receptionist, an office attendant, a sales girl, as shared by the respondents. The transitory phase included adolescent girls’ conflict with self and family to bargain for their aspirations as the girls reported during the visits. This conflict has led some of them to reinterpret the cultural hurdles as prescribed by the community through bargaining and resisting to achieve their aspirations in life. This in turn has resulted in girls’ making efforts to strategise and negotiate for their right to exercise their agency in education, work, and marriage.

Discussion and Concluding Remarks

Adolescence is the stage known for drastic physical changes and identity formation. This is the time when a child develops an abstract understanding of self in relation to society and so starts forming a wider world view about self in relation to the wider society. Here, the school is introduced mainly as the state institution in reference to the government initiatives taken for educational development of Muslim girls in the community. Subsequently, school acts as a secondary socialising agency and is also termed as the most likely social institution that provides opportunities for democratic practices (Carnoy &

Levin, 1985). Growing up with minimal civic infrastructure in the habitation and studying in school with an all Muslim student population has inculcated a more generalised sense of understanding about the social order around in an urban setting (Flanagan.et.al, 2007).

The study reveals that school as a state institution offers a socialising space beyond home to Muslim girls, where they learn and share with peers and form aspirations—largely in affirmation with the family ideals—of class and gender. Some girls use the space to make their voices heard not only in school, but also at home. But many girls comply with the expectations of school as well as family. The girls undergo the struggle of pursuing aspirations or reconstructing from the parents’ perspective, which they expressed in their expectations from parents. Everyday interactions in school with teachers and peers differ a lot from the everyday interaction with family at home and so the disconnect between these two core stakeholders persists. The school functions in a ritualistic manner (Maclern, 1999) as reflected in its school culture and fulfils the gendered expectations of the family for girls through discipline. The everyday nuances in school and home continue to perpetuate the broader social realities in a very subtle manner—authority structure in school and home in relation to their education and career aspirations for Muslim girls in Shahbadpur.

The study showed how the poverty driven vicious cycle for the community girls keep them entrapped as a barrier in exploring life beyond home through education. Few girls who were resisting in schools kept their aspirations high even after completing school education and bargained with their families for the same. At the same time, other girls were left to reconstruct their aspirations related to education and work. Especially girls from the vocational stream, who learned and got training in a skill, that is Beauty Culture and Health, had to withdraw from the regular mode of education system. This showed that the State’s efforts on exploring the possibilities of developing skill among Muslim girl students are ultimately lending them to opt for home-based work, that too if required (according to parents) in the habitation. The state’s agendas of empowering Muslim girls have been half-heartedly addressed; the girls in this study find some resemblance with Paul Willis’ (1977) subject participants who are finally learning to labour within homes.

It is the vicious cycle of macro and micro socio-economic factors that is contributing in maintaining the status-quo for Muslim girls who receive school education under constrained circumstances. The study finds a complex overlapping of the “class” factor when girls who can’t afford expensive coaching for Science and Commerce are compelled to take up Arts, and girls with scores less than 60 per cent at secondary level are given the vocational stream. Allocation of gendered areas of vocation like Beauty Culture and

Health and Textile Designing in the name of imparting skill for Muslim girls' empowerment in a way contributes in reproducing gender and class for the community girls. So, the sustaining socio-economic backwardness has nothing to do with the community's religious association. The girls under the study are socialised to strengthen their gendered role in contemporary times and so fail to realise their aspirations to reach university, which could have been the case for girls belonging to other faiths as well. School and home work hand-in-hand in reproducing class and gender for the community girls. Thus, in two schools, for girls enrolled in the vocational stream, there is limited awareness about the career prospects for vocational streams at senior secondary level, in terms of the possibility of pursuing vocational education at higher education level. Interestingly, for all the girls (Arts and Vocational streams) college means pursuing Bachelors in Arts (B.A. programme), which they aspire but fail to do. This is how the entry into a university for a regular graduate programme remained an elusive goal and university still remains an exclusionary space for many girls belonging to the largest religious minority in terms of access to higher education.

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